

A RAPID METHOD OF ESTIMATING TUNGSTEN IN TUNGSTEN STEELS.

BY DURGA PADA CHATTERJEE.

For the quick estimation of tungsten in tungsten-steels (high speed steels or self-hardening steels as they are called) a method has been evolved in which tungsten is oxidised to tungstic acid, dissolved in excess of caustic alkali, the excess of which is back titrated by a standard acid, glycerol and mannitol being used to prevent hydrolysis.

Steel-borings (2g.) are dissolved in 60 c.c. of concentrated HCl. When the solution is almost complete HNO_3 is added drop by drop for oxidation and the solution evaporated with occasional addition of drops of nitric acid. Yellow precipitate of WO_3 comes out. The concentrated solution is then diluted with 100 c.c. of 10% HCl solution when heavy precipitation occurs. This is filtered through paper pulp (Swedish paper pulp being preferable), and washed with 1% NaCl solution till free from acid. It is then mixed with 50 c.c. of warm water with 40 c.c. of neutral glycerol or 1.5 g. of mannitol and vigorously shaken. $N/10$ -NaOH solution is then added with constant stirring till the yellow precipitate goes into solution and the liquid becomes colourless. The excess of NaOH is then titrated by $N/10$ -HCl

This method has been found to be applicable to steels containing as much as 4 to 20% of tungsten.

The author's thanks are due to Mr. C. H. Shvitcliff, the Head of the Laboratory for his encouragement and interest.

ORDNANCE LABORATORY,
ICHAPUR, BRNGAL.

Received March 5, 1940.

